

Critical Making

D6.1 CRITICAL MAKING SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY FRAMEWORK FOR PROJECT EVALUATION

About this document

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Critical Making

LIST OF ACRONYMS AND ABBREVIATIONS

CM	Critical Making
DIY	Do-It-Yourself
DoA	Description of Action
DoW	Description of Work
GIG	Global Innovation Gathering e.V., Germany
GIM	Grass-roots Innovation Movements
H2020	Horizon2020 – The European Research Framework Programme
RDI	Research, Development and Innovation
RRI	Responsible Research and Innovation
SDGs	Sustainable Development Goals
STEM	Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics
TUB	Technische Universität Berlin, Germany
VTT	Teknologian Tutkimuskeskus VTT OY, Finland
WIF	Wikifactory Europe SL, Spain
WP	Work Package
WP1	Project Management
WP2	Building the critical making knowledge-base: concept & methods
WP3	Case Action: GENDER
WP4	Case Action: YOUNG TALENTS
WP5	Case Action: OPENNESS
WP6	Evaluation, Impact, Future Implications
WP7	Dissemination, Exploitation and Communication
WS	Workshop
ZSI	Zentrum für Soziale Innovation, Austria

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The main aim of the Critical Making project is to foster criticality in making and at the same time support the responsibility of the global maker movement and local makers and makerspaces by co-creating tailored RRI principles and practices for makers in collaboration with the Critical Making project team and practitioners. The Critical Making evaluation framework introduced in this document is an essential part in achieving these goals. It

1) outlines the general RRI and SDG goals of the project as well as specific goals for the three case action work packages focusing on gender, youth and openness in making,

2) introduces the co-evaluation approach which enables the consortium members to follow the impacts of case activities and to learn from the feedback throughout the case actions and

3) presents the evaluation process and measures for each of the case actions and

4) outlines how the evaluation framework is used and elaborated during the project to guarantee the responsibility of the project itself and to achieve the goals of the project.

The Critical Making evaluation framework draws insights from the two basic approaches that have been agreed on and collaboratively created with the consortium during the year 2021: ***the critical making responsibility framework*** created in the consortium during the year 2021 and introduced

in the deliverable 2.1. The Critical Making responsibility is based on a dialogue between the RRI competences and four GIM dimensions and serves as a theoretical background in formulating case specific evaluation goals and questions. The other guiding principle is **co-evaluation**, which means that the case action participants will be engaged in conducting the evaluation and have been included also in the creation of this evaluation framework. In addition to evaluating the RRI aspects of our case actions, we will also apply **SDG framework** to reflect the potential long- and short-term impacts of the project and to translate the broad SDG goals into meaningful measures and indicators for grass roots innovation initiatives. We bring all these three approaches together to build a new framework that suits the goals of our project: supports the projects inclusive, open and reflexive implementation.

This Evaluation framework document presents how we have adapted the above mentioned three starting points to the three Critical Making case action work packages. It introduces the evaluation process, engaged actors, specific goals and related measures, data collection methods and timelines. In addition to case specific descriptions, the document also presents how we bring together the evidence from evaluation of the case actions and based on this contribute to creating an approach to RRI and SDGs that can be applied with grass-roots initiatives more broadly. Following from this, our work contributes to existing RRI evaluation frameworks including MoRRI and SuperMoRRI. Furthermore, it provides insight on how grass-roots actors can measure their contribution to broader SDG goals.

1. INTRODUCTION

The global maker movement has grown and gained more visibility during recent years. The movement is all about tinkering, building, repairing and sharing knowledge around the practice. Although many makers make simply because it is fun, there is also a more serious and radical side to the movement: making can challenge currently prevalent production systems and even create a new industrial revolution (Troxler 2013).

The main aim of the Critical Making project is to strengthen the criticality of the maker movement. We define critical making, in accordance with Max Ratto, who originally coined the term, as the combination of critical thinking and making. For Ratto, Critical Making shifts the focus from purely making to critical reflections of what is being made. In critical making, the objects being made can be used as reflection points. In this way, making is used as a way to engage in discussing ethical issues and societal debates, for example. (See Ratto 2011).

In the Critical Making project, our aim is to foster criticality in making and at the same time support the responsibility of the global maker movement and local maker activities by co-creating tailored RRI principles and practices for makers in collaboration with the Critical Making project team and practitioners. In the first phase of the project in the year 2021, we mapped the current state of RRI related practices in the maker movement (see deliverables 2.1, 3.1, 4.1 and 6.1) and based on that background work, interventions to address issues related to selected RRI topics of gender, engagement of youth and openness in making have been co-designed together with a variety of stakeholders.

The Critical Making evaluation framework introduced in this document is an integral and essential part in achieving the responsibility goals of the project. It 1) outlines the general RRI and SDG goals of the project as well as specific

goals for each case action, 2) introduces the co-evaluation approach which enables the consortium members to follow the impacts of case activities and to learn from the feedback throughout the case actions and 3) presents the evaluation process and measures for each of the case actions.

2. GENERAL STARTING POINTS OF THE EVALUATION

2.1. KEY PRINCIPLES OF CRITICAL MAKING

Critical Making is a very central concept to the whole project and thus also for the evaluation. Originally the term was coined by Matt Ratto (2011). For him critical making meant a shift from purely making to also or even mainly critically reflecting what is being made. Understood in this way, critical making shifts the focus away from products and uses making as a tool of reflection. Ratto used the term especially in the context of education, where making could be used as a tool for discussing difficult problems (Ratto 2011). The term has also been associated with DIY citizenship (Ratto & Boler 2014) and making that is more radical and political than usually (Hertz 2015).

The Critical Making consortium has also drafted its own working definition of the term critical making. In this definition, the two parts of the term are highlighted: critical thinking and making. Making is defined as “a technology-based extension of DIY culture” (p. 31 of deliverable D2.1 Critical Making Baseline). Criticality is here defined through five distinct factors, namely: local and connected, social, critical, impactful and joyful/meaningful (ibid). This definition of critical making guides also the creation of this evaluation framework.

Defined like this, critical making is still a relatively wide concept with many possible points of intervention. For the Critical Making project, three focus points have been selected. These are: gender sensitivity, engagement of youth through formal and informal education and openness on making. The gender aspect of the project focuses on increasing the maker movement’s gender inclusiveness through co-designed interventions. The work package focusing on youth will organise interventions that will help increase criticality of educational maker practises as well as educate teachers about critical

making and foster collaboration between schools and maker spaces. The third focus point, openness, is promoted by organising a mentoring program that aims at increasing participants' ability to critically reflect on their making practises and help them increase the quality and outreach of documentation that makes it easier for other makers to replicate what they have made.

The three focus points have been structured under three work packages that will each carry out interventions to advance the chosen goals through critical making. At the same time, the case action interventions provide us an opportunity to experiment how different evaluation practices support responsibility and learning in maker spaces. As the case actions have somewhat different methodologies, the evaluation framework is adapted for the needs of each work package. The evaluation of different case actions will feed into a common understanding and the overall development of the Critical Making evaluation framework. The evaluation framework draws insights from the two basic approaches that have been agreed on and collaboratively created with the consortium during the year 2021: the critical making responsibility framework and co-evaluation. In the following, we will briefly introduce these starting points before going into detailed description of the evaluation framework.

2.2: OVERARCHING METHODOLOGICAL PRINCIPLE: CO-EVALUATION

As RRI and related public engagement values are central for the project, it was clear from the start that the case action participants will be engaged in conducting the evaluation, not only project partners. The creation of the evaluation framework is also something that we want to do collaboratively, so that the evaluation questions posed for different work packages eventually reflect the goals and values of those engaged. Therefore, we have chosen, to follow the principles of co-evaluation in the evaluation process design.

According to Mayer et al. (2021) and Schaefer et al. (2021), co-evaluation puts focus on co-creating the evaluation questions and process. Therefore, this

approach is very well in line with the co-creation of other activities in the Critical Making project. In a similar manner than in other co-creation activities, co-evaluation also emphasises the process of collectively defining the goals, values and expected impacts of project activities. Co-evaluation ensures that all relevant stakeholder groups are heard in defining the most important outcomes and impacts of a project. In this way, it is a fundamentally different compared to a more traditional, top-down approach where researchers alone define the important targets and measures (Schaefer et al. 2021).

In Critical Making, the planning of evaluation actions is partially embedded with other co-creation activities. As the engagement actions with citizens and makers take place in each case action work package separately, the co-evaluation process also looks slightly different for each of these. The details of co-evaluation are described in the chapter 3 before the work package specifically adapted frameworks are introduced.

Even though Critical Making is not a citizen science project in its most traditional sense, engaging different citizen groups and communities, including groups that are often underrepresented in research contexts, is in the very core of the project. Therefore the evaluation methods traditionally used in citizen science are a good reference point for Critical Making also. Citizen science projects have been evaluated using a wide range of different methods, such as surveys, interviews, participant observations and self-reflection (Schaefer et al. 2021, p. 502). We will apply a variety of these methods also in the evaluation of Critical Making case actions.

2.3. CRITICAL MAKING RESPONSIBILITY FRAMEWORK: COMBINATION OF RRI & GIM

Our evaluation framework is tailored for Critical Making by combining insights from three broader theoretical frameworks. Firstly, we draw from the general Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) framework that has originally been designed to foster social responsibility of institutional

research funding and research performing organisations (Gianni, Pearson & Reber 2019). The core idea of RRI is to increase the communication between researchers and other societal stakeholders throughout the process. Furthermore, the RRI framework which is frequently applied in the EU funding introduces six RRI keys that need to be considered when designing and performing RDI activities and in implementing or communicating their results (see figure 1 below). Various RRI indicators have been developed during the recent years to evaluate how well research addresses the different RRI keys (e.g. MORRI, SuperMORRI). Because these indicators are developed for the purposes of institutional research organisations they are not, however applicable for grass roots innovation activities and making. Therefore, we will develop our own indicators to monitor the issues of ethics, gender equality, science education, public engagement and open access in a way which best suits the context of grass roots innovations and Critical Making case actions.

Figure 1. RRI keys

The RRI key dimension ***ethics*** describes ethical considerations that are important in the course of any research process. The goal of ethical considerations is to ensure that research and innovation activities are carried out in a socially and ethically acceptable manner. It is central here to align the values of research organisations and processes to those of the surrounding society. Research and innovation activities should always be considerate of their social and societal impacts and make sure they contribute to a desirable future.

The RRI key dimension ***gender*** focuses on gender balances and breaking down gendered barriers to participation. To create a more gender balanced future, attention needs to be paid to gendered structures that might prevent some groups from taking part in decision making and other societally relevant activities. This emphasises the importance of reflecting on gender-related factors during research projects and also evaluating the actual gender balances during project activities.

The RRI key dimension ***public engagement*** highlights the importance of having a wide range of different actors take part in research and innovation processes. Wide participation from different sectors of society ensures that a process is diverse in terms of values and interests represented. Citizens and other parties should be seen as research partners and potential collaborators in making research and innovation projects, not only as passive recipients of final outcomes. In this way research and innovation is more likely to bring to society towards a future desirable to a wide range of societal actors.

The RRI key dimension ***science education*** focuses on expanding citizens understanding of science as well as promoting scientific careers. Ensuring citizens have enough understanding of scientific processes and research enables them to take part in scientific discussions and understand new scientific developments. Understanding of scientific processes is also

beneficial from a point of view of citizen science projects and expanding the subjectivity of citizens in many societal arenas.

The last RRI key dimension that is brought to our evaluation framework is ***open access***. This key dimension emphasises the importance of open sharing of knowledge and accessibility of scientific information. Openness of scientific results can improve the quality of science, but also make it easier to include wide range of societal actors into science debates and other societally relevant discussions. Free access to scientific, peer-reviewed articles is part of these goals. On the other hand, giving access to scientific data to other researchers is also perceived to be important.

The RRI key dimension *governance* is not brought to our evaluation framework. This key factor concerns, as the name suggests, the governance of research and innovation ecosystems and the societal environments where these activities take place. For Critical Making case actions, this RRI key does not offer new, relevant perspectives that could help in building a more responsible research process.

Focus on RRI competences

In addition to defining the six RRI keys, the recent RRI literature has also emphasised the deliberative character of RRI processes and the so called procedural RRI criteria related to RRI competences (Stilgoe et al. 2013, Tassone et al. 2018). We find that these competences provide a good starting point to Critical Making evaluation practices to design evaluation questions to increase the reflexivity and anticipatory capacity of makers. Therefore, in addition to tailoring indicators suitable to monitor the five RRI keys in making, we will keep in mind the procedural and competence focused insight offered by RRI approach (see figure 2) and adopt the principles of anticipation, reflexivity, inclusion and responsiveness in the design of the Critical Making evaluation framework.

Figure 2. RRI competences

Following from the failure of the existing RRI approach to grasp the specifics of grass roots innovations (see, eg. Bhaduri & Thalal 2020), we have cross-fertilised the competence-oriented responsibility criteria of RRI approach (anticipation, reflexivity, inclusiveness and responsiveness) with the in-depth understanding of which factors affect the dynamics of grass-roots innovations offered by the Grass Roots Innovation Movement framework (GIM). Grassroots innovation movements are special in their stance outside institutions. Still, they hold a remarkable amount of agency, working in a bottom-up manner to solve local problems and sharing knowledge in a more open and understandable way compared to most institutionalized forms of knowledge-sharing. Our approach to grassroots innovation movements stems from the one presented by Smith et al. (2017). They use four analytical starting points when talking about grassroots innovation movements, as seen in Figure 3. These are: spaces and strategies, pathways, contexts, and framings.

Figure 3. GIM framework

To deepen our understanding of RRI in the particular context of making, we have created a Critical Making Responsibility Framework, which is based on a dialogue between the RRI competences and four GIM dimensions. The framework is introduced in table 1 and described in more detail in the deliverables 2.1 and 2.2. It will serve as a theoretical background in formulating case specific evaluation goals and questions. At the same time, the adequacy of the framework will be tested during the case action evaluations and the framework will be elaborated in the end of the project based on the lessons learnt during the project.

Table 1. The Critical Making Responsibility Framework.

		RRI Competence			
		Anticipation	Reflexivity	Inclusiveness	Responsiveness
GIM dimension	Context	CONTEXT x ANTICIPATION Ability to understand and act upon the on-going changes in social, historical, political, economic, cultural, religious contexts (trends & weak signals) and other circumstances and what kind of opportunities, restrictions and requirements they may provide in the future.	CONTEXT x REFLEXIVITY To become aware of how social, historical, political, economic, cultural and religious contexts have affected one's activities (innovations, projects etc.) and what kinds of contexts their reactions & innovations might create, (e.g. vicious circles or hope, and for whom?)	CONTEXT x INCLUSIVENESS To become aware of exclusive, contextual patterns - to understand that you don't by accident exclude others (like women, elderly, etc.) - understanding how exclusion works and supporting people based on the contextual patterns of exclusion	CONTEXT x RESPONSIVENESS To understand the particular societal needs arising from the context and to respond to them through making & innovations and in addition knowing "how to react and whom to contact to influence the societal rules of the game.
	Framings	FRAMINGS x ANTICIPATION	FRAMINGS x REFLEXIVITY To become aware of how used language and terminology shapes the taken actions and what kinds of values and interests are mobilized, maintained or challenged with the language used. Shared framings can help and hinder dialogues and once that is recognized, something new can be learned.	FRAMINGS x INCLUSIVENESS To reflect upon and become aware of the wordings that are used, or the setup of the space, and whether they create inclusion or exclusion? Does the shared umbrella of interpretation lead to missing any perspectives?	FRAMINGS x RESPONSIVENESS
	Spaces and	SPACES/STRATEGIES x ANTICIPATION	SPACES/STRATEGIES x REFLEXIVITY To become aware of how chosen strategies	SPACES/STRATEGIES x INCLUSIVENESS	SPACES/STRATEGIES x RESPONSIVENESS

	strategies	To become aware of one's own strategies to act, to learn to deliberately build strategies towards desired futures and to be able to anticipate what kinds of futures (and future spaces of action) the applied strategies create.	influence other people or environment - what are the risks and rewards for the surrounding community and environment of the chosen strategies	To become aware of the norms and conventions that "made the space" of making & innovations: if excludes someone, become aware of these norms and conventions, physical structures and language.	To explore how available resources will influence what you do (skills in the team; tools available) and how to act to expand them.
	Pathways	<p>PATHWAYS x ANTICIPATION</p> <p>To become more aware of what sort of pathways are supported: what future pathways are made while doing concrete projects, and reflect upon the potential plurality of it, to anticipate the impact of the ethical pathways. To recognize the path dependencies, become aware of what one can change with the created pathway and what not.</p>	<p>PATHWAYS x REFLEXIVITY</p> <p>To become aware of one's own role and the situatedness of the activities carried out: how those impact/influence the environment. By recognizing the various pathways (anticipation), the potential social and ecological impacts can be reflected upon.</p>	<p>PATHWAYS x INCLUSIVENESS</p> <p>To reflect upon whether the developed or imagined pathways maintain existing exclusive structures, do they create new exclusions, new divisions between people? How can they be made more inclusive?</p>	<p>PATHWAYS x RESPONSIVENESS</p> <p>To investigate what kind of support the desired pathways would need in the broader social context (knowledge, funding, policy changes etc.) and/ or whether they may face resistance and to consider how this support can be gained and resistance addressed.</p>

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The benefits of combining RRI & GIM approaches in evaluation

The benefits of bringing together GIM and RRI frameworks in Critical Making lies in the power of the GIM approach in helping us asking questions that are better suited for grassroots innovation initiatives, as this unique perspective is lacking from RRI and SDG frameworks. However, GIM does not offer specific indicators to measure these movements. Even though we tailor make indicators for RRI and SDG goals as well, this difference is seen in our different approach to these frameworks. For GIM, we will not offer any concrete indicators. Instead, the GIM framework is used in guiding us in asking the right questions. The GIM framework helps in mapping the environment in which grassroots innovation initiatives work. Therefore it is a valuable help in ensuring we are measuring and evaluating all the things that are crucial for maker communities.

2.4. EVALUATION OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT GOALS

In addition to chosen RRI factors relevant for making, we also aim to evaluate the SDG impacts of Critical Making case actions. Sustainable development goals are United Nation's set of 17 targets that are designed to present globally shared goals for social, economic and environmental development. These goals were adopted in 2015 and the time limit for their realisation is set to 2030. The 17 SDG goals cover a wide range of issues from eliminating poverty globally to protecting oceans and preserving economic growth.

Similarly to RRI keys, the SDGs are quite general and operate at the level where direct connections to grass roots activities may be difficult to identify or measure. Therefore, when applying SDGs to individual project activities, not all the goals can or should be targeted at once. Instead, a few, well suited goals can be picked that represent the objectives of certain projects or activities. The 17 main SDGs are divided to 169 more concrete targets. As the SDG targets are originally made for measurement in country level, these will not be used in our evaluation framework. We will operate at the level of the

17 main SDG goals and will tailor in collaboration with our stakeholders new indicators that suit the project nature of Critical Making and are applicable to grass roots activities.

When measuring SDG impacts, not all goals are usually pursued in one project. This is also the case for Critical Making. Already in the planning phase of the project, five SDGs were recognised as important for the project. These were SDG 5 Gender equality, SDG 8 Decent work and economic growth, SDG 9 Industry, innovation and infrastructure, SDG 10 Reduced inequalities and SDG 12 Responsible consumption and production. When finally starting to draft the evaluation framework, one additional SDG goal (SDG 4 Quality education) was identified as significant to especially work package 4 that deals with children and youth in making. To have concrete measurements of how to target these goals, we developed new indicators, which will be described in the following sections.

Figure 4. SDG goals most relevant in Critical Making

2.5 COMBINING THE DIFFERENT APPROACHES

As seen, the different approaches taken as starting points of evaluating the case actions of Critical Making have somewhat different angles to sustainability and responsibility. RRI emphasises ethics and social responsibility during the research process and when evaluating the end results. SDG framework, on the other hand, places more focus on impacts on environmental as well as social sustainability. GIM framework is used as a resource to provide us understanding of the context of grassroots innovations. We bring all these three approaches together to build a new framework that suits the goals of our project: supports the projects inclusive, open and reflexive implementation.

Different aspects of RRI and SDG are covered explicitly in our evaluation framework for the Critical Making case actions. We have paid attention to the RRI keys and SDG goals so that all relevant factors are present in our evaluation framework. In addition, we have used the Critical Making responsibility framework created in WP2 and related RRI&GIM matrix to identify important reflexive questions for each case action.

3. CO-DESIGNING THE CRITICAL MAKING EVALUATION FRAMEWORK

The creation of the evaluation framework has been a collaborative process, engaging all consortium members, but also participants of case actions (WP3) and other stakeholders interested in the project (WP5). A number of different co-creation workshops have been organised to define the most important sustainability questions and the scope of the evaluation of Critical Making. The collaboration has started before drafting the concrete contents of the evaluation framework, by mapping the different partners' hopes and expectations for the project during the consortium meeting at 4-5.10 2022 in Vienna.

3.1. SETTING THE FOCUS OF EVALUATION

The first thing to be decided during the co-design of the evaluation framework was the scope of evaluation. The big question here was between evaluating the whole project or mainly focusing on the case action work packages. As the Critical Making KPI indicators already cover the whole project, we did not perceive it important to set more similar goals in the evaluation framework for the project. In addition, as the case actions are the core activity of the project, the touchpoints where the project has an opportunity to make a difference in its target groups, to interact with makers, collect their ideas and hopes, to learn from the practitioners and hopefully to give back knowledge and tools, the key focus of the evaluation framework is in the case actions.

As described above, the project has three case action work packages; gender, young talents and openness. Each of these focuses on different RRI themes and carries out different interventions. Therefore, the common evaluation framework has also been adapted to suit the specific needs of each work package. In each work package, a common structure has been followed

(defining actors, goals, measures, data collection processes) and the principle of co-design has been practiced. To facilitate cross-action learning, we will arrange knowledge exchange workshops in the midterm and in the end of case actions. In the end, the framework will create a comprehensive approach to measuring RRI and SDG aspects when working with grass-roots movements.

3.2. CONSTRUCTING THE EVALUATION FRAMEWORK FOR WORK PACKAGES

The building of the evaluation framework started with carefully going through the work plans and deliverables of all work packages. The aims of each case action work package were analysed and a list of preliminary evaluation questions was formed based on these. The preliminary evaluation questions were shared with each work package in the consortium in October 2021 in Vienna, to collect their comments, ideas and feedback for the key learning targets of evaluation. An example of this process can be seen in the figure 5. In addition to deepening the understanding of the goals of case action evaluation, we also arranged a discussion to clarify consortium members' hopes and ambitions regarding the whole Critical Making project. In this discussion, common themes and new perspectives were discovered. The results of the discussion will be detailed more at the section 3.3.

After the consortium meeting, the learnings were analysed by the WP6 team. As the case action work packages were at different stages of planning, the building of the evaluation frames for each package also took slightly different paths. For all the work packages, however, a collaborative discussion workshop was arranged, where the findings from the consortium meeting were developed further. For the case action work packages concerning youth and gender, this meant taking a step back and creating a clearer understanding of the actions that will be evaluated, the target groups that will be engaged and the most important sustainability issues and evaluation questions that are related to these. For the case action work package on openness, the process was already more clearly defined, and the discussion

could be structured more around formulating actual evaluation questions and identifying the points of data collection.

After these workshops, we drafted adapted evaluation frames for the case actions, which will be presented in detail in Section 4 below. These drafts were then again discussed with each work package to gain a common agreement of how the evaluation will take place.

Sustainability questions for WPS Openness

Question/indicator	Possible measure	RRI Key dimension	SDG	Critical Making focus point
Degrees of openness of produced hardware designs in the mentoring program	there could be a tool in Vici's lists??? <i>Open-0-meter</i>	Open access	SDG 9 Industry, innovation and infrastructure	Openness
Societal relevance of the innovations generated during the mentoring program	a self-reflection tool → end interviews → SDG relevant to the innovation	Ethics	SDG 9 Industry, innovation and infrastructure; SDG 12 Responsible consumption and production	Reflexivity
Financial viability of the innovations generated during the mentoring program	<i>Businessmodel applied</i> <i>Reflection tool</i>		SDG 8 Decent work and economic growth	
Participants understanding of open source hardware	the survey	Open access		Openness
Ethical and ecological considerations of the life cycles of innovations generated during the mentoring program	<i>reflection tool</i>	Ethics	SDG 12 Responsible consumption and production	Reflexivity
Share of women and non-binary persons in the mentoring program	share of women and non-binary persons → ask people about identification	Gender	SDG 5 Gender equality	Gender
Participants in Mentoring program	number of...			
Applications for Mentoring program	number of...	public engagement		Inclusiveness

Figure 5. An example of co-designing the evaluation questions

3.3. SPECIFYING THE MAIN GOALS AND SUSTAINABILITY QUESTIONS

Although the evaluation framework is built separately for different work packages, there is also some common ground of the sustainability questions that concern the whole project. These goals partially stem already from the proposal phase of the project. Also, a discussion of the main goals and

expected outcomes of the project was held during a consortium meeting in October 2021. In this discussion, the expectations that different partners have for the project were mapped.

Figure 6. Goals of the project as discussed in consortium meeting in 2021

In figure 6 the answers of project partners to a question “What would make this project successful?” are presented. As can be seen from the picture, there were some common themes recognised that did surface in many of the answers. In the following, we present a version of the goals of the whole project that is adapted of the results of this discussion. The goals that were recognised during the consortium meeting were formulated into five distinct focus points, and these focus points have been discussed with all the work packages during the design process of the evaluation framework. Based on this process, we identified the following main goals of the whole Critical Making project.

4. **Community creation.** We want to help makers build long-lasting communities and create new contacts, both locally and globally. We want to support current makerspaces in their community building, using their platforms and letting them have their own pace. We also wish to create or strengthen communality around critical making

among teachers and support the online communities of makers, through e.g. the Wikifactory platform.

5. **Inclusiveness.** We want to help create a more diverse maker community. We want to consider intersectionality, including gender diversity and socioeconomic backgrounds. We want to support cooperation of global north and south. We want to consider the practices that shut certain groups out or make it uncomfortable for them to participate in making practices. We also want to share this knowledge and understanding into the maker communities we work with.
6. **Critical Making education.** We want to bring critical making more to the education system, both in schools and universities. Especially we want to target university students who will be schoolteachers. We also want to educate makers about critical making. Raising makers' reflexivity is a part of this.
7. **Openness.** We work mainly with open hardware, and as a research project we want to be doing our part for open science. Openness work package is especially concerned with this, but other work packages consider these questions as well. We see openness as one of the main pillars of the maker movement.
8. **Raising awareness.** We want to raise the publics' awareness of critical making. We also want to raise critical making more into the funding schemes of EU.

These goals are wider than the scope of the case actions. However, these goals are well kept in mind while shaping the more specific goals of different case actions.

4. WP3 – GENDER

4.1 INTRODUCTION OF THE CASE ACTIONS AND GOALS OF THE WORK PACKAGE

In WP3 we aim to explore gender inequalities in the maker movement and identify strategies on how to address the currently perceived gender bias in makerspaces. We aim to co-design and implement gender-related activities that cover a broad spectrum of gender-related aspects and are co-created bottom up - which means identified, designed and implemented by representatives of the maker community themselves.

With this aim, we started our work with a collection and review of existing initiatives and programmes, on- and offline, that aim to engage and accept female, inter*, trans, and non-binary persons in the community of responsible innovators and makers. We analysed these activities using the GIM framework mentioned above to better understand pathways, framings, activities and contexts of these initiatives.

In a second step we invited representatives of these initiatives to a series of three co-design workshops. At the beginning of these workshops, we presented the results of our GIM analysis and then involved 12 participants into the following design steps:

Workshop 1: a brainstorming of how the ideal future related to gender and making would look like; an identification of activities that would help to support this ideal future of gender in making.

Workshop 2: a more detailed elaboration and prioritisation of these activities that support gender-inclusivity in making, collection of first good and bad practises related to these activities

Workshop 3: a selection of four activities (case actions) that will be implemented and evaluated throughout the Critical Making project with support by the workshop participants.

The process of this workshop series and its outcomes are presented in detail in the upcoming report D3.2. The four case actions selected through this process for the gender work package are:

Case Action 1: Caretaker-inclusive making

In this case representatives of the maker community elaborate new engagement formats that allow caretakers to get involved in making, while their children either take part in the making endeavour or can play in a supervised and adequate way.

Case Action 2: Speaker Series

In this case representatives of the German maker community work on a series of talks where makers from marginalised positions share their experiences in making with the aim to reach out to and attract a broader audience to making.

Case Action 3: Outreach material

In this case representatives of the maker community will elaborate outreach material to create visibility for gender inclusive making, share insights about its potential and provide guidance on how to best facilitate gender inclusive making.

Case Action 4: Support existing maker spaces in gender-inclusive making

In this case two makerspaces from Africa will be supported in their outreach to female makers, to develop new formats of engaging them, providing funding for these events and the facilitation of these people.

In addition to these four cases, a 5th case action has already been defined in the DoW:

Case Action 5: Making the Wikifactory platform more gender inclusive.

In this case actions lessons learned from the WP3 activities will be continually reflected together with community managers and implementers of

wikifactory in order to adapt the Wikifactory platform to be more gender inclusive.

The co-designed and selected case actions are an important basis for the evaluation and impact assessment plan. The objectives of WP6 are twofold:

- to understand how far the four implemented case actions support gender-inclusiveness in making.
- to analyse the implemented case actions related to the core concepts of the GIM and RRI framework.

4.2 THE EVALUATION FRAMEWORK – QUESTIONS AND MEASUREMENTS

In the following section we will present the evaluation frameworks for each of the gender cases and then discuss the commonalities and differences between these.

Group 1: Making with Parents

Activities	Engaged Actors	Expected impact/ outcome	Measures/ indicators	Who measures?	When is measured?	What data is produced?
Karolina 3 hours open workshop for parents - time for kids with babywearing: 15 minutes (max 3 hours)	- FabLab educators - Ined Babylab, - Orange Foundation (mybke)	offer for parents included 4th regular activities - activities are well promoted and known by parents in the area - the offer is independent from grants and is commercialised to communicate to parents about the possibilities, even projects with their own parents, we need to be supported by a network of the parents that have their own space	- at least 10 parents participating in a workshop weekly - 20% of parents increased the focus and creativity during the activities 80% of parents notice possibility to develop their skills for personal and professional level	-FabLab social project's manager		- quantitative data - how many parents are interested in the offer, how many hours a week they can spend to develop their projects if they are offered help; - qualitative data - discovering the link between the creative development of the parent and the fact of having a child - creating surveys for parents to evaluate e.g. from 1 to 10 how much this activity help them to focus
Ira Give mothers/elder pre tutorial or introduction Agree with mothers, it can be a product exact after the workshop (I will release their needs like to do it)	Mothers Mothers/babes and/or collectives/community as Kids	Mothers and their kids will do experiment and exploration	20 mothers and kids from different backgrounds, divided in to a group/observation to have a bond between mother and kids for critical thoughts To make each family the awareness about critical making	Project Coordinator of the events/venues	before and after the introduction for the big group, then the workshop for each small group)	Age, interest, actually, tasks a hardware that they need, content (how they feel to work in the lab with their mother), Future Project The excitement, the coordination, the relation between parents and kids, the spaces
Stefanie food workshop Unleashing, making, modification, testing, testing, with, they do it in a creative way, they give feedback to the group, with kids, something a product that is made with their own hands, with a real meaning or repair something, in case one gets relaxed, there should be some drinks and give provided for kids and parents	more like a four fix parents, kids, maybe not much other stuff to keep it cheap and simple	agree with Ira: has to be hybrid, so that parts can be prepared during a walk or in a park keep people in the community, give support to each other, stop isolation of care-takers, kids not hurting themselves, mothers focusing on something else than their kids	be outspoken about welcoming people with small kids, start a debate, learn from the process, refine and calibrate	project coordinator of the event	after a month and then again after three months	do kids come again? do they want to stay? Are they parents relaxed or even more multitasking than usual? are people feeling empowered?

Figure 7: Setting up the evaluation of gender case action 1

Figure 7 is an outcome of a brainstorming session about the evaluation of the case action, which is presented in more detail in the following table 2.

Case action 1: Foster Caretaker-inclusive Making

In this case action three different formats for caretaker-inclusive making will be developed.

Table 2: Evaluation framework of gender case action 1

Activities	Engaged Actors	Expected impact	Measures	Responsible	Time points	Produced data
2 hours open workshops (WS) for caretakers; In these 2 hours a babysitter takes care of children Caretakers are upfront informed about past projects so they can start preparing first ideas at home	Fablab educators Babysitter Caretakers Children	Caretaker WS are included in regular activities WS are well known by caretakers in the region WS are independent from grants and commercialised Caretakers get to know the ideation process, they have the possibility to get	> 10 caretakers participate in weekly workshop > 20% of them say that it increased their focus and creativity > 50% of them notice the possibility to increase their skills (personal and professional)	Fablab social project managers	Continuously tracking of numbers Questionnaires distributed to participants after the workshops	No. of interested caretakers No. of hours spent on make-projects per week Questionnaire data that help to understand the WS impact on focus, creativity and skills

		involved in making				
<p>WS where mothers make something together with their children Mothers/elders get an introduction and pre tutorial before they work in smaller groups</p> <p>The WS ends with a potluck event</p>	<p>Makerspace/hackerspace/collectives/communities</p> <p>Mothers Mothers Children</p>	<p>Mothers and their children explore and experiment together</p> <p>Participants have an increased awareness about CM</p> <p>They have a bond between mothers and children for critical thoughts</p>	<p>20 mothers and children from different background participate in 4 groups/sessions Raised awareness for critical making</p> <p>Raised interest in experimenting</p> <p>Joyful experience</p>	<p>Project coordinator of the events</p>	<p>Questionnaire or interviews collect feedback before and after the introduction (for the big group)</p> <p>and after the workshop (for each smaller group)</p>	<p>No. of participating mothers and kids, age, interest, hardware and tools they used, inclusivity</p> <p>Data capturing excitement, continuation, relation between mothers and children, openness, comfort, future projects</p>
<p>“Messy lab” jour fixe for caretakers and children;</p> <p>To tinker, make music/noise, use soil, water, dough, make food (things that cannot be done with children at home)</p>	<p>Project coordinator</p> <p>Caretakers</p> <p>Children</p>	<p>Keep caretakers engaged in the maker community</p> <p>Give support to each other, stop isolation of caretakers</p> <p>Allow mothers to focus on</p>	<p>Regular number of participants in the jour fixes</p> <p>Interest in exploring and experimenting amongst mothers and children</p> <p>Perceived support</p>	<p>Project coordinator of the events</p>	<p>Questionnaire or interviews collect feedback after a month and then again after three months</p>	<p>No. of participating caretakers and children, age, interest, tools used etc.</p> <p>Observation: Do children come again? Do they want to stay? Are</p>

<p>Combining a printed out website with regular, real meetings;</p> <p>Hybrid format so that parts can be prepared during a walk or in a park.</p>		<p>something else than their children</p> <p>Allow children to experiment without hurting themselves</p> <p>Learn from the process and refine it</p>	<p>and being embedded in a community</p> <p>Joyful experience</p>			<p>they crying a lot? Are the caretakers relaxed or even more multitasking than usual?</p> <p>Questionnaire/Interview: Do participants feel empowered, embedded, interested ...</p>
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Case action 2: Organise Speaker Series

In this case action four events with underrepresented speakers of the make community are planned in different makerspaces in Germany.

Group 2: Speaker Series

Figure 8: Setting up the evaluation of gender case action 2

Figure 8 is an outcome of a brainstorming session about the evaluation of the case action, which is presented in more detail in the following table 3.

Table 3: Evaluation framework of gender case action 2

Activities	Engaged Actors	Expected impact	Measures	Responsible	Time points	Produced data
4 events with a range of different speakers who represent a great diversity per event	Speakers from a marginalised position (not white, cis dyadic male and well-educated)	People from different socio- cultural and technological fields are engaged as speakers	Heterogeneity of speakers achieved	Event coordinators on site	A very short survey is distributed during the event to the audience and another one to the speakers	No. of participants, socio-cultural background, technological fields, new to the make spaces, etc.
Organised in Stratum0, XHain and 2 other makerspaces in Germany	Speakers from outside Europe	A new audience is reached who wants to learn about plural visions coming from plural backgrounds	New audiences reached		Follow up 2-3 months after the event for both groups via questionnaire or interview	Survey data on motivational drivers of participation and direct impact of event participation
Taking place in spring/summer to allow for physical events and creating connections between participants and spaces	A diverse audience listening to the speakers	Makerspaces learn what it needs to get new audiences (what is the trigger, what makes people feel that they can join without being a "nerd"?)	Identified measures to reach new audiences			Survey data on longer-term impact (e.g. does audience come back to makerspace, get involved in making, stays in contact with some
	Project coordinators in makerspaces	Increased exchange between makerspaces in Germany	Awareness for new perspectives			
		Audience understands that it does not need a	Awareness that make scene is not so easily accessible for everyone			
			Knowledge about new technological			

		technical degree to be part of hacking/making, and that not everyone has it that easy to get started	fields			of the participants etc.)
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Case action 3: Create Outreach Material

This case action will elaborate two different outreach materials: One will be a manual for gender-inclusive making, the other one a selection of success stories of gender inclusive making.

Group 3: Outreach Material

Figure 9: Setting up the evaluation of gender case action 3.

Figure 9 is an outcome of a brainstorming session about the evaluation of the case action, which is presented in more detail in the following table 4.

Table 4: Evaluation framework of gender case action 3

Activities	Engaged Actors	Expected impact	Measures	Responsible	Time points	Produced data
<p>Create a manual how to support gender-inclusivity in making</p> <p>Potentially with a checklist for the self-evaluation of spaces</p>	<p>People from the make community</p> <p>People running the spaces</p>	<p>Greater awareness for gender-inclusiveness in the make community</p> <p>Increased knowledge how to foster gender-inclusiveness</p> <p>More people representing marginalised groups joining the make community</p>	<p>No. of downloads and views of the manual</p> <p>Perceived usefulness and understandability</p> <p>Effectiveness of manual (e.g. short term changes implemented)</p> <p>Increased awareness and knowledge of space organisers</p>	<p>Core team of outreach group together with peer community, e.g. “friendly spaces”.</p> <p>These “friendly spaces” use the checklist, plan a feedback workshop and use the guidelines</p>	<p>Peer review of final draft version to get feedback on usefulness and understandability</p> <p>Specific feedback workshops with makerspaces to ask for evaluation of the manual</p> <p>Continuous access statistic</p>	<p>Quantitative data from access statistics</p> <p>Qualitative feedback from peer review, workshop participants and people running the “friendly spaces”</p>
<p>Explore success stories for marginalised target groups</p> <p>Conduct short interviews with</p>	<p>People introduced in success stories</p> <p>Reached target groups: young people not in</p>	<p>Increased awareness about the possibilities in make spaces by people representing marginalised groups</p>	<p>No. of downloads and views on platforms (e.g. LinkedIn)</p> <p>Feedback of the people viewing the</p>	<p>Core team of outreach group</p> <p>Maybe in close interaction with WP4 Young talents</p>	<p>Continuous access statistic and social media tracing</p> <p>Selected interviews with audience after</p>	<p>Quantitative data from access statistics</p> <p>Qualitative feedback from audience</p>

<p>success stories people</p> <p>Disseminate the success stories as online zines</p>	<p>makerspaces yet and entrepreneurs</p>	<p>Increased interested and engagement in make spaces</p> <p>Increased interest in entrepreneurial activities</p>	<p>success stories</p>		<p>publication</p>	<p>collected in selected interviews and via social media</p>
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Case action 4: Support existing make spaces with gender-inclusive making

In this case action, two different formats are developed: one is a workshop series that involves women in Cameroon in make activities of the MboaLab; and in the other format local female brewers team up with local teachers and the innovation centre GoGirls ICT to develop hand sanitizers in South Sudan.

Group 4: Support existing make spaces with their activities

Figure 10: Setting up the evaluation of gender case action 4.

Table 5: Evaluation framework of gender case action 4

Activities	Engaged Actors	Expected impact	Measures	Responsible	Time points	Produced data
<p>3-days workshop to engage more women in CM (3D printing, laser cutting, coding ...)</p> <p>Collect and share existing critical making ideas</p> <p>Half-day event with GoGirls ICT to share experiences on hand-sanitizers</p>	<p>Secondary school girls</p> <p>Women from rural areas</p> <p>Women in academia</p> <p>MboaLab educators</p>	<p>More women visit MboaLab and get involved in making</p> <p>Design and documentation of tools that are useful to all women</p> <p>More engagement and collaboration of MboaLab with the local secondary school</p> <p>Process documentation</p>	<p>No. of participants joining the WS and returning to the lab</p> <p>No. of tools produced</p> <p>Feedback of participants on</p> <p>Future collaborations with local secondary school</p> <p>Downloads of documentations</p>	Event coordinator on site	Before, during and after the event	<p>Quantitative data from observation</p> <p>Quantitative and qualitative data from survey and interview: Motivation Perceived usefulness of event and designed tools New knowledge Interest and engagement</p>
Start activity of producing hand sanitizer with local female brewers and science	<p>Female brewers</p> <p>Science teachers</p> <p>Lab staff</p>	<p>Knowledge transfer from Mboalab to the actors in GoGirls ICT</p> <p>Production of hand sanitizer by local</p>	Increased knowledge and transferability of lessons learned from MboaLab to the GoGirls ICT	Coordinator on site	Continuous collection of feedback and numbers starting in February	<p>Quantitative data from observation</p> <p>Qualitative data from interviews: Perceived</p>

<p>teachers</p> <p>Half-day event with MboaLab to learn from their experiences on hand-sanitizers</p>		<p>brewers in cooperation with science teachers</p> <p>Increased interest in STEM by women</p>	<p>context</p> <p>No. of Participants involved in production of hand sanitizer</p> <p>No. of hand sanitizer produced</p>			<p>usefulness</p> <p>Increased knowledge</p> <p>Implementation of lessons learned</p> <p>Increased interest in STEM</p>
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Case action 5: Increase gender-inclusivity on the Wikifactory platform

In this case action the goal is to foster a more gender-inclusive online community of makers by continuously adapting the Wikifactory platform. We will also document the process of implementing a gender-inclusive online community related to making and technology and learn from this process.

Table 6: Evaluation framework of gender case action 5.

Activities	Engaged Actors	Expected impact	Measures	Responsible	Time points	Produced data
Adaptation of the wikifactory platform to be more gender-inclusive (e.g. wording, used images, presented projects, and offered functions)	Wikifactory communication manager and technical staff Wikifactory community members	Increasing no. of people representing marginalised groups joining the wikifactory community More critical making projects and activities presented on the platform Better understanding how to drive gender-inclusivity in the online world	No. of community members from marginalised groups No. of critical making projects Documented process of platform, its drivers and challenges	Wikifactory project manager	Continuous	Access statistics of the platform Observation of projects, profiles, topics Documentation of the change process

Summary of evaluation and impact assessment in WP3

The previous chapters showed that the case actions that will be implemented in the second project year of the Critical Making project differ largely with regard to their activities, involved stakeholders and measures of success.

Nevertheless they all serve the overarching goal to support gender-inclusiveness in making and technology and to learn how this can best take place. The following table summarises the inputs from the 5 case actions and adds an overall layer of the expected impact of the gender work package.

Table 7: Summary of evaluation actions of WP3.

Activities	Engaged Actors	Expected impact	Measures	Produced data
Elaborate new workshop formats for caretaker-inclusive making in Poland, Austria and Indonesia	Maker-/Hackerspace organisers, educators and members	Increase awareness about CM and that it does not require specific skills to take part	No. of new community members representing marginalised groups actively involved, returning to the make spaces, presenting themselves online	Quantitative data from counting participants, views on resources etc.
Elaborate a workshop format that fosters women's engagement in making in Cameroon	People representing marginalised groups in making (e.g. female, inter*, trans, and non-binary persons, caretakers, children)	Engage new audiences representing marginalised groups in the make community	No. of critical making projects documented and shared on- and offline	Quantitative/qualitative data from collecting feedback of participants via questionnaires and interviews
	Critical Making	Foster exploration and experimentation in making and technology amongst marginalised groups	No. of gender-inclusive formats/methods documented and shared	Observations of participants and documentation of process

<p>Involve women in making Handsanitizers in South-Sudan</p> <p>Create a handbook for gender-inclusive making</p> <p>Create success stories of gender-inclusive making online</p> <p>Organise a speaker series of marginalised makers in Germany</p> <p>Adapt the wikifactory platform</p> <p>Analyse the case actions using the Critical Making Responsibility Framework</p>	<p>consortium partners</p>	<p>Learn about plural visions coming from plural backgrounds related to the potentials of making and technology</p> <p>Support creating things that are of use for the participants</p> <p>Increase exchange between makerspaces and cooperations with other local actors</p> <p>Document and share experiences as open educational resources</p> <p>Create awareness for the topic of gender inclusiveness in the maker community amongst makerspace organisers</p> <p>Learn about the new engagement formats and processes and adapt them accordingly</p> <p>Learn what it needs to get new audiences to makerspaces</p> <p>Understand processes that drive gender-inclusive making online</p>	<p>Downloads/views of educational resources and outreach material</p> <p>Future collaborations established</p> <p>Perceived usefulness and understandability of outreach material, experienced impact from applying the guidelines</p> <p>Perceive usefulness from workshop formats and speaker series, experienced impact of participants and organisers</p> <p>Increases in awareness, knowledge and skills in gender-inclusive, critical making</p> <p>Interest in exploring and experimenting</p> <p>Joyful experience</p> <p>No. of cases analysed using the Critical Making Responsibility Framework and lessons learned documented and shared</p>	<p>Key aspects and lessons learned in driving gender-inclusive making (by applying the Critical Making Responsibility Framework)</p>
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		Understand importance of GIM/RRR aspects for driving gender-inclusive making		
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5. WP4 – YOUTH

5.1 INTRODUCTION OF CASE ACTIONS AND GOALS OF WORK PACKAGE

The aim of the work package 4 is to foster the engagement of young people in making and particularly in reflexive critical making. To reach this broader goal, we have chosen to focus our interventions on teachers and teacher educators who are in a key position to reach a large number of children with diverse background, introduce making for children and apply the tools of making in science and tech education. Furthermore, we aim to build connections between schools and makerspaces and to support the pedagogical skills of makerspaces. In summary, the goals of WP4 are the following:

- 1) increase the awareness of teacher educators, teaching students and teachers on critical making and the opportunities to engage making for the curriculum of schools
- 2) to engage teacher educators, teaching students and teachers in making, to enable them to experience the joy of making and to encourage them to apply methods of critical making in education
- 3) to support the sharing of best practices of maker education among teacher educators, teachers and maker space operators and actors
- 4) to support community building of teachers and makerspace actors interested in training young people
- 5) to support the pedagogical skills of makerspace actors engaged in providing training and workshops for children and young people

To efficiently reach the aimed target groups, the planned case interventions will be integrated in the in the on-going actions of TU Berlin, GIG and Wikifactory which already have an extensive network of stakeholders in teacher education and local and international maker spaces having an interest in working with children and youth. Following from this focus, the

face to face case actions will be held in Germany and in German language. In addition, we will produce podcast material and guidelines for maker education targeting broader international audience.

The planned case actions include:

Case action 1: Critical Making events in the Bildung, Bits & Bäume student festival

The festival will be held in September 2022 in Berlin focusing on digital education and pairing of Maker education and SDGs. Critical Making collaborates with J Junge Tüftler*innen and Innovation Education Lab that are maker spaces experienced in working with children with a particular focus on sustainability and digitalisation. The aim of the workshop is to increase the awareness of critical making among teacher educators and teaching students and to enable them to experience and experiment with the methods of critical making. In addition, the event aims to build connections with maker spaces and teacher educators. The details of the festival event are still in progress in the beginning of the year 2022 and the final plan will be developed by the end of April.

Case action 2: Podcast on Critical making for educators

During the year 2022, we will release a series of podcasts providing insights on the principles, opportunities, tools, methods and experiences of applying critical making in teaching. The podcasts will be designed, produced and hosted by the TUBerlin team and disseminated through various platforms to enable a broad outreach. The main target group for the podcasts are teachers, teacher trainers at High Education Institutions, and those still in training to become teachers. The topics will be picked dynamically and based on “hot topics” in the public discourse. Currently the podcasts are expected

to be held in German, and potentially some in English to address a wider, more international, audience.

Case action 3: Critical making manifesto

The third intervention in WP4 is the development and dissemination of Guidelines for Critical Making education targeting for a wider, global audience, including schools, makerspaces, higher education organisations educating teachers and makerspaces and fablabs. At the first phase, the guidelines will be delivered in the form of a Critical Making manifesto, collecting the main principles of critical making into a visually interesting poster that can be distributed through various platforms and printed on the walls of schools, universities, makerspaces and fablabs. The manifesto will also be disseminated through Wikifactory platform, with an aim to engage 10 interesting universities to share it. Furthermore, we will establish a discussion group in Wikifactory around the manifesto to collect feedback. Based on these discussions and learnings from other case actions, the manifesto will be elaborated into guidelines at the end of the project.

Case action 4: Pedagogical training for makerspaces

Our fourth case action will consist of trainings directed to makerspace and fablab operators and actors who are focusing on working with children to support their pedagogical skills and ability to engage children with diverse background into making in a meaningful and inclusive way. The training workshops will be held in Germany, either face to face or on-line depending. The contents and methods of the training sessions will be co-designed in March-April 2022 with relevant makerspace actors and during that co-design the detailed goals and evaluation measures for this case action will also be clarified.

5.2 EVALUATION OF THE CASE ACTIONS

The original aim of the Critical Making consortium was to run case interventions as face to face workshops and training sessions in schools and universities in Germany, but due to the difficulties caused by the pandemic we have been forced to redesign our case actions from the original plans of the Critical Making DoA. Following from this, the planning and co-design of the case interventions is still on-going in the beginning of the year 2022. The detailed goals and implementation plans will be developed by the end of April. At this phase, we have done the preliminary identification of the main impacts and measures and planned a preliminary monitoring and data collection plan for each case action. These are presented in the table 8. This plan will serve as a basis for the development of the final evaluation guideline (including survey questions and interview guidelines) for WP4 case actions in April 2022, well before the interventions start.

Table 8. Evaluation actions of WP4.

Activities	Engaged actors	Expected impact	Measures	Responsible	Time points	Produced data
Bildung, bits & bäume festival	Teacher educators Teacher students Teachers	Getting more teachers interested in making Encouraging teacher students to make Spark teacher students to hack Community building to support making in education Increasing diversity in maker education	Number of presentations in the festival Number of students participating Number of teacher educators participating Number of teachers participating Diversity of participants (gender, age) Diversity of topics of presentations Social media outreach/ number of critical making hits in social media channel	Critical making WP 4 team	Tracking during the festival Tracking the follow-up events 1 year after the festival	Quantitative data of the number of participants and their background during the festival Quantitative data of social media hits during the festival Feedback survey (mobile app) data from the participants in the end of festival Open qualitative feedback from participants for a poster during the festival

			Participants experience the joy and usefulness of making			
			Follow-up activities			
Podcast for educators	Higher education teachers teaching in universities Teachers	Increasing knowledge of making in education Increasing understanding of critical making	Outreach/ number of listeners Number of uploads Number of shares in social media Geographical diversity of listeners Number of questions/comments/ feedback from the audience Diversity of addressed topics	Critical making WP4 team	Continuous tracking after the release of podcasts	Quantitative data on social media actions Qualitative data on the topics of feedback comments

Critical Making manifesto -	University teachers School teachers Makerspaces	Increasing understanding of critical making in schools & maker spaces	Number of uploads Number of shares in social media Number of higher education institutions engaging in discussions Intensity of discussion in social media channels on the manifesto (including Wikifactory group) Teachers', teacher educators' & maker space learnings of critical making	Critical making WP4 team Engaged higher education institutions Engaged maker spaces	Continuous tracking of social media after the launch of the guidelines Feedback surveys at the time of the release of the guidelines in universities & maker spaces	Quantitative social media tracking data Quantitative and qualitative feedback data on the contents of the manifesto from universities & maker spaces
Training for makers on how to educate	Maker spaces Fablabs focusing on children	Increasing the pedagogical skills of maker spaces Increasing awareness of maker spaces in schools	Number of participants in training Diversity of participants in training (gender, age) New maker education skills learned by makers	Critical Making WP4 team Engaged maker spaces	Entry & end surveys of participants of training Follow up survey 6 months after the training	Quantitative & qualitative feedback data from the entry, end & follow up surveys Quantitative social media hit data

	<p>Non-institutional teachers</p> <p>Teachers</p> <p>Teacher students</p> <p>Children and youth participating in making experiments</p>	<p>Incorporate making in the curriculum of schools</p>	<p>New maker education skills learned by teachers</p> <p>Number of making activities in engaged schools</p> <p>Increasing awareness of Critical Making education in social media</p>		<p>occurrence of #critical making during and one month after the training</p>	
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Critical Making

6. WP5 - OPENNESS

6.1 INTRODUCTION AND GOALS OF THE MENTORING WORKSHOP SERIES

As the main activity of the Openness work package, we will arrange a Critical Making mentoring program. The idea is to offer makers an opportunity to gain more skills and knowledge about open hardware, opening up of their practices and reflexivity that could lead to more sustainable making. The goal will be achieved through mentoring workshops with varying mentors. The workshop series is co-designed in two co-design workshops with makers and makerspace leaders interested.

There will be three categories in which potential mentees can apply for the program: environmental sustainability, social innovation and open science. The exact outline of each category is still to be determined based on the co-design sessions. The workshop series will be structured around the five critical making principles recognised in an earlier co-creation event by GIG in December 2019. The five principles can be seen below in figure 10. This way the mentoring workshop series will cover a wide range of relevant responsibility themes.

1. **Make** things that make sense: Create products and solutions that solve fundamental, real-world problems.
2. **Integrate** Local Knowledge: Design with the community, leveraging on local knowledge and experience, as well as the local resources & assets available.
3. **Include** Ecosystem Services: Aim to give back more than you take from the environment and include accounting practices that value the natural resources used.
4. **Build** for Continuity: Design for the present and future; build social capacity & aim for financial self-sufficiency.
5. **Share** How You Make: Develop a set of guidelines that provide a framework for openly documenting everything about the making of the project.

Figure 11: 5 Principles of making

As the design process is still on-going, not all details of the mentoring program are ready. Two co-design sessions with makers and makerspace actors interested in developing the program have been arranged. Based on the conversations in the co-design sessions, the following basic principles have been drafted:

- 3 categories, 36 mentees who are makers (in a wide sense: people who make something) and want to get mentoring on their on-going making project
- During the program the mentees learn about sustainability and openness and how to implement better practices in their making – adding a critical aspect to their making
- Each workshop will have a different mentor who is an expert in the specific topic
- One of the benefits is the interaction, collaboration and sharing good practices with other makers
- Everything will be online and global maker community is targeted

Figure 12. The timeline of the mentoring program, as presented in co-design sessions in 12/2021 and 1/2022

6.2 THE EVALUATION PROCESS AND FRAMEWORK

The evaluation process of WP5 is structured by the mentoring program that is the main activity of the work package. The first activities that will be evaluated are the co-design workshops where the mentoring program is planned together with makers and makerspace actors. In this phase, the most important thing is to have a wide representation of actors involved, so that different perspectives can be included into the design. In the mentoring program, a wider set of evaluation questions will be used. RRI and SDG indicators are utilised as starting points of creating the evaluation questions, and different aspects are covered.

In table 9, the basic starting points of the evaluation of WP5 are presented. As is stated in the table, there are two main activities that are evaluated in WP5: the co-design workshops and the Open Hardware mentoring program. The mentoring program is evaluated in a more detailed manner. The evaluation of the mentoring workshop will give valuable information for not only the overall evaluation of our project, but also help learning from the experience of arranging a mentoring program and provide guidance for any similar future initiatives.

To guide the forming of concrete evaluation questions the engaged actors, expected impacts and details of evaluation process have been first drafted,

as presented in table 9 below. As the mentoring program of WP5 is already planned in sufficient details, the evaluation is also already planned in more detail than with other work packages. Therefore tables with exact evaluation questions that will be used in different phases of the evaluation process are presented in following chapters. The connections of the evaluation questions to RRI dimensions and SDGs is also already mapped.

Table 9: Overall evaluation framework of WP5.

Activities	Engaged Actors	Expected impact	Measures	Responsible	Time points	Produced data
Co-Design workshops	Active makers and makerspace leaders GIG members	Creating a mentoring workshop series that is relevant to makers	No. of co-design workshop participants Diversity of co-design participants	Co-design workshop coordinators	During co-design session	Basic quantitative data about participants: country of residence, gender
Open Hardware mentoring program	Makers and hackers wanting to showcase what they have made Makers looking to communicate their sustainability values to funders Makers wanting to be more sustainable/responsible	Increasing participants understanding of critical making /sustainability Networking Participants being better able to scale up Better communication about sustainability values Improved	Quality of projects produced Feedback from workshops Inclusivity of program Quality of documentation produced	Coordinators of the mentoring program / the workshops	Interviews in the beginning and end of the mentoring program Short surveys after each workshop	Qualitative interview data Basic quantitative survey data: satisfaction with the mentoring etc.

		replicability of projects				
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Co-design workshops

The first action to be evaluated is the co-design workshops. As explained above, there has been two of such workshops, during which the process, potential participants and important topics for the mentoring program have been defined. The participants of the co-design workshops have been makers and makerspace leaders who have volunteered to share their expertise. In the first workshop, six participants were present, and in the second workshop nine.

The evaluation of the co-design workshops is mostly based on the background information of the participants. As one of the most important qualities of the co-design process is its inclusiveness and representativeness of the global maker movement we want to target, special attention was paid to these attributes. In addition, the participants were encouraged to give feedback about the co-design process at the end of the second workshop.

Table 10: Evaluation questions of co-design workshops of WP5.

Measure	Question/ indicator	RRI key dimension
Number of participants in co-design workshops	number of participants in both workshops	public engagement
Gender distribution of co-design actions	multiple choice: male/female/gender diverse	gender
Geographical diversity of co-design participants	number of countries/continents represented	ethics

Participants' experience of the workshop	collecting free form feedback at the end of the second workshop	ethics
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Recruitment process

We want to make sure our recruitment process is as inclusive, fair and ethical as possible. The recruitment of participants is a crucial point in the mentoring workshop as it determines who will get the chance to benefit from the mentoring in the first place. If the recruitment process is not inclusive, fair and ethical, the impact of the whole program is severely compromised. This is why it is important to carefully evaluate the success of the recruitment process.

Table 11: Evaluation questions related to the recruitment process of WP5 mentoring program.

Measure	Question/ indicator	RRI key dimension
Inclusivity of communication about the mentoring program, considering e.g. cultural minorities and people with disabilities	a reflection for the coordinators of the program	ethics
Gender distribution of applicants	multiple choice in the application form: male/female/gender diverse	gender
Geographical diversity of applicants	country/continent of residence of applicants, asked in the application form	ethics
Inclusivity of the program for people with less financial capital	a reflection question for program coordinators	ethics

Entry and exit interviews

We will interview all mentoring program participants twice, in the beginning and the end of the mentoring program. In these interviews, the reflection tool first introduced in deliverable D2.1 will be used as a starting point for discussions. The tool has been developed further since the submission of the deliverable. A test simulation of the reflection tool was carried out in the consortium meeting in October 2021. Also, a co-design session with stakeholders, mainly consisting of the GIG network of makers and makerspace leaders, was organised. However, the reflection tool is still in process of development and is intended to be developed still further during the project.

As the reflection tool as such is made for makerspace actors to evaluate their own actions, it does not necessarily cover all aspects that we want to evaluate in our project. To test the overall functionality of the reflection tool and to develop it further, we still want to use it as a starting point of conversation in our interviews. To cover all relevant aspects, however, some additional specifying questions are added in this context. The questions might also be altered after first interviews if it is purposeful. As we gain deeper understanding about using the reflection tool, it will also be developed further.

In earlier stages of the mentoring program, only RRI indicators have been presented so far. In the entry and exit interviews, we will also reflect how participants' projects contribute to broader sustainability goals. This provides us an opportunity elaborate such SDG indicators that are meaningful from the perspective of grass roots innovations. We have identified at the design phase three different SDG that are relevant for the mentoring programme projects but these may change at the course of time when we learn more from the mentees aims and project plans.

Table 12: Evaluation questions for entry and exit interviews.

Measure	Question to be asked	RRI key dimension	SDG goal
<i>Make Things that Make Sense</i>			
Societal relevance of innovations generated/worked on during the mentoring program	Will your project have a fundamental impact or is it rather a fun project or both?	Ethics	SDG 12 Responsible consumption and production
Long-term commitment to maker activities	Is your project/ activity generating long-term commitment? Or how could you ensure long-term engagement in the future?	<i>Community empowerment</i>	
The joy/ enjoyment of making	Do you feel joy when engaging in your project/activity? Do others? Where does this joy or enjoyment stem from?	<i>Community empowerment</i>	
<i>Include Ecosystem Services</i>			
Ethical and ecological considerations of the life cycles of innovations worked on	How will your project affect your surroundings (both nature and people) during its life cycle?	Ethics	SDG 12 Responsible consumption and production
Anticipation of unintended consequences	What unintended consequences of your project/activity to the environment or people around you could be foreseen? How could these be managed?	Ethics	SDG 12 Responsible consumption and production
<i>Build to be Self-Sustainable</i>			
Financial viability of projects/activities worked on	Is your project/ activity reliant on external support?		SDG 8 Decent work and economic growth
Future financial viability	Do you have plans to make your project/activity self-sustaining? How clear and realistic are those plans?		SDG 8 Decent work and economic growth

Share How You Make			
Participants' level of sharing	How do you share what/how you make? (self-reflection tool has options)	open access	
Degrees of openness	open-o-meter	open access	
Replicability of open hardware	Could others replicate or remix your makes based on your documentation?	open access	
Participants' understanding of open hardware	Are you familiar with the concept of open hardware? Do you use it/feel like it is a good concept?	open access	
Integrate Local Knowledge			
Embeddedness in the local society/community	Is the local society/ community present in your project/ activity?	public engagement	
Including local materials	Do you consider materials locally available when designing?	ethics	
Participant's understanding of inclusiveness	What kind of maker practices would you describe as inclusive?	ethics	
Inclusiveness of participants' activities	Do you consider special groups (people with disabilities, people with limited financial capital, ethnic minorities etc.) in your project/activity? Do you target these groups with your activities/innovations?	ethics	SDG 9 – Industry, innovation and infrastructure

Short questionnaires after each workshop

As stated before, the mentoring program will consist of five workshops, each of which covers a distinct theme. Each workshop will have a unique mentor with expertise in the area. The workshops are planned to take about half a day, but the exact details will be decided once the mentors are selected. This way every mentoring workshop will be a unique learning experience.

For the evaluation of the mentoring workshops, short questionnaires are planned to be filled out after each workshop. These could not only give us and the mentors valuable information about how the mentoring workshops have succeeded but also be a quick moment of reflection for the participants. We do not want to put additional pressure on the participants in a form of long survey forms, so the questionnaires will only contain a few, easy-to-answer questions. The exact formulation of questions will still be re-shaped as the exact contents of each workshop are drafted. Initial evaluation questions are, however, drafted already as following:

- Was the workshop useful for you?
- Was the workshop enjoyable for you?
- Did you get new ideas for how to make your making more sustainable?
- Did you feel like different groups and individuals were addressed in a proper and inclusive manner before and during the workshop?
- Do you have anything else you want to tell us about this workshop?
Please give us any feedback!

These questions would give instant feedback on how relevant and successful the workshops are. Instant feedback could also give a chance to better things for later workshop sessions. The questions drafted above also contribute to evaluating the projects compliance with RRI key dimensions (ethics, community empowerment). The data gathered from the workshops can then

be combined with interview data gathered before and after the program. As the workshops exact contents are still to be designed, the relating evaluation questions also are only preliminary at this stage.

7. OVERALL CONTRIBUTIONS TO RRI AND SDG FRAMEWORKS

Finally, we wish to bring evidence from evaluation of the different activities together and contribute to creating an approach to RRI and SDGs that can be applied with grass-roots initiatives. Following from this, our work contributes to existing RRI evaluation frameworks including MoRRI and SuperMoRRI. Furthermore, it provides insight on how grass-roots actors can measure their contribution to broader SDG goals. In the following, our current understanding of the connections between our measures and indicators and selected RRI keys/SDGs is presented. As the project's evaluation is only now beginning, the understanding will develop within the coming two years.

One of the basic divisions that we understand to be central in RRI and SDG evaluations is the difference between evaluating the (research) process and the impacts of the project. RRI is designed to be used in evaluating and supporting the responsibility of research and innovation processes at the course of RDI activities. Even though grass-roots innovations form a distinct field of action, the process is still the part covered by RRI evaluation. SDGs, on the other hand, have been designed to be used to measuring the short and long-term outcomes of a project, i.e. impact at a more macro level. Measuring such impacts related to grass-roots initiatives does require completely new indicators and a new way of thinking. Therefore, we will also tailor new SDG indicators to measure the impacts of the project. These initial indicators will be further tested and elaborated with actors engaged in case actions. To promote the grass root level perspective to SDGs, we will

collaborate closely with other EU-funded projects (i.e. FRANCIS) with similar aims, and disseminate our results together.

In the tables 13 and 14, the current understanding of the evaluation's connection to RRI keys and SDGs is presented. As each work package is different in their scope of action and targeted impact, they are also presented separately.

Concerning RRI, one of the goals of WP6 is to create new set of indicators that can be used in grass-roots level. As stated before, we use the five relevant RRI key dimensions as the base of this work. As introduced earlier in the description of the co-creation process of the evaluation framework, the starting point for identifying measures and evaluation questions for each work package was a careful analysis of the actors involved and the targeted impacts. Based on this understanding, first indicators were drafted. RRI and SDGs were only then brought into the picture.

From this starting point, we identified a need for measuring procedural questions that were not covered by any of the current RRI key dimensions. These questions have to do with one of the special attributes of grass-roots initiatives: ***the centrality of community***. A functioning community with committed members is one of the most important corner stones of grass-roots innovation movements, and therefore projects working with these communities should also take community empowerment seriously. Empowered grass-roots communities have a feeling of capability when it comes to creating changes in the society and they hold the keys to maintaining their functionality in the long term. Therefore we propose a new dimension, community empowerment, could be added to RRI keys when applying them to grass-roots movements. We will test this idea while gathering data from the case actions and discussing with different RRI stakeholders. In table 14 some possible indicators measuring this dimension are presented for all work packages.

Table 13. The RRI key dimensions and relating evaluation questions.

Critical Making

<i>RRI key dimensions</i>			
	<i>WP3</i>	<i>WP4</i>	<i>WP5</i>
Ethics	Increasing participants' awareness of critical making Increasing awareness of the barriers to participating in making Achieving diverse participant group	Geographical diversity of publics reached/people involved	Ensuring geographical diversity of participants Reflecting on the barriers to fully inclusive practice Increasing the participants awareness of sustainability and responsibility issues
Gender equality	Aiming for gender-diverse participants	Diversity of participants	Gender distribution of participants
Open access	Learning from prior initiatives		Level of openness of activities during the mentoring program Increasing the participants' awareness of openness of hardware
Public engagement	Number of participants in workshops Reaching new audiences Number of downloads of online contents	Number of student festival participants Social media outreach and download/share numbers of online contents	Number of community members engaging Engaging local communities in participating projects
Science education	Offering learning opportunities for children	Supporting and monitoring maker education in schools & pedagogical readiness of makerspaces	
Community empowerment	Creating joyful experiences Generating long-term participation Creating a supportive community	Creating interest among teachers & new ways of sharing knowledge and ideas	The ability to generate long-term commitment to maker communities

Table 14. Relevant SDG goals and relating evaluation questions.

<i>SDGs</i>			
	<i>WP3</i>	<i>WP4</i>	<i>WP5</i>
SDG 4 – Quality education	Generating interest towards making in children	Teachers gaining better understanding of critical making education Creating bonds between makers and education to support innovation activities and learning	
SDG 5 – Gender	Creating new opportunities for caretakers with small children to participate Monitoring changes inspired by gender-inclusivity manual		
SDG 8 – Decent work and economic growth			Financial viability of makerspace innovations designed during mentoring program
SDG 9 – Industry, innovation and infrastructure	Creating innovation possibilities in a more gender inclusive manner	New innovation capabilities created for the youth	Inclusion of different groups in innovation activities
SDG 10 – Reduced inequalities	Creating awareness of barriers to participating in making Enabling production of hand-sanitizer locally		
SDG 12 – Sustainable consumption and production	Local, responsible hand-sanitizer production		Ensuring the responsibility of makerspace innovations designed during mentoring program Increasing participants’ understanding of sustainability aspects of maker activities

Critical Making

In table 13, we present the main connections between RRI key dimensions and the evaluation frameworks of different work packages. As can be seen, all the case action work packages share several goals, even though they are formulated in a slightly different manner in different work packages. All WPs aim at geographically diverse and gender representative participant group, for example. Public engagement is also an important goal for all WPs, and things like number of participants is monitored in all WPs. All the WPs also have some goals related to community empowerment, that is, creating a sustained engagement and generating positive experiences of working with maker communities. Open access is understandably most important for WP5 that deals with the openness practices of the maker movement. For WP3 openness in a form of sharing and learning from prior scientific works is also recognised as important. The RRI key of science education is recognised to be important in both WP3 and WP4, as both work with children, encouraging them to making and learning about science.

Table 14, on the other hand, presents the connections between SDGs and the evaluation frameworks of case action WPs. There are six SDGs that are generally recognised as important to Critical Making project. As the WPs have different scopes of action, they also hold different potential for impact. SDG 4, quality education, is the most important for WP4 that specifically aims at developing maker education in schools through engaging teachers and teacher students. SDG 5, gender, is the most important for WP3 that aims at creating a lasting impact in a form of more gender inclusive maker practices. In our context of grass-roots innovation activities, SDG 8, decent work and economic growth, is understood as creating a financially viable solutions for makerspace organisations to work. SDG 9, industry, innovation and infrastructure, on the other hand, has to do with creating more inclusive maker practices, as WPs 3 and 5 aim at doing. SDG 10, reduced inequalities, specifically has to do with creating a more financially just world, that in the context of our project can be understood as more (financially) equal access

to activities, manufacturing and products such as hand sanitisers. Finally, SDG 12, Responsible consumption and production, is addressed in WPs 3 and 5 as more sustainable maker practices are sought to be established.

All in all the experience of creating RRI and SDG based indicators to evaluate a project working with grass-roots innovation movement has so far showed that these frameworks are fitting for this purpose. Although some adapting is necessary, RRI and SDG approaches probe relevant questions for this field of study. As the evaluation framework is further developed and used during the project, we will gather more insights into these topics and the RRI and SDG links will also develop further.

8. OUTLOOK

The Critical Making evaluation framework aims to support the following targets:

1. To ensure that the project respects the principles of responsible research
2. To support the monitoring and on-going learning during the Critical Making case interventions within work packages and across work packages
3. To feed input for the elaboration of Critical Making responsibility framework (GIMxRRI matrix)
4. To contribute to general RRI discussions and indicator development with an RRI & SDG indicator basket that is particularly tailored for the context of grass roots innovations and making
5. To feed input for the development of RRI guidelines for grass roots innovations

In every stage of the project and its evaluation, ethical viewpoints are considered. As we engage a wider audience into our project activities, having their informed consent and treating them with respect and fairness is crucial. This also includes ensuring that all participants are aware of the evaluation actions carried out and are informed about the aims of this process. The ethical guidelines of Critical Making are described in more details in D1.1.

To make sure, that we reach the learning goals and manage to contribute to the theoretical RRI discussion, we will in the future proceed with the evaluation in the following way:

Evaluation team; regular follow-ups

Each work package has been nominated a person that is responsible of the application of evaluation framework during the case interventions: these are Teresa Schäfer for WP3, Alexander Kutschera for WP4 and Hanna Saari for WP5. Together with the WP6 work package leader and Critical Making co-

ordinator, they form an evaluation co-ordination team, which follows in bi-weekly basis the data collection and monitoring of case actions. The evaluation framework will also be introduced for the evaluation experts of the advisory board in March 2022 to collect their comments and input.

Finalisation of detailed data collection plans for case actions

This evaluation framework sets up the basic approach for case action evaluations. Due to differences between the work packages, there are differences also in the level of details described in the framework. The evaluation co-ordination team will take care that the survey and interview guides and questions will be ready for the data collection in a timely manner throughout the case actions. In addition, the team will discuss the and accept changes in the evaluation plans if needed.

Cross-action learning and knowledge exchange

WP6 will arrange two knowledge exchange workshops to support cross action learning during the case interventions. The first one will take place in June when many of the WP3 case actions have already started and the Open hardware mentoring programme of WP5 is on-going. Based on the first experiences, the aim is to reflect what kind of RRI issues have been faced during the project and how well does our responsibility framework address these issues and offer support for tackling them. In addition, mid case intervention workshop is also a good occasion to reconsider the potential risks and uncertainties related to case actions. The second cross-action learning workshop will take place in December 2022 when the interventions are all conducted. The aim of that workshop is to elaborate the learnings of evaluation.

Contribution to the elaboration of Critical Making responsibility framework

The lessons learnt from the case action evaluation will provide valuable input for the WP2 effort of elaborating the analytical Critical Making responsibility framework. Based on case action evaluations, we can validate how well our

primary interpretations of GIM & procedural RRI dimensions address different responsibility issues to arise during grass roots innovations and making in various societal contexts and modify the GIM-RRI matrix. This work will be finalised in the spring 2023.

RRI guidelines for grass roots innovations

The final output of WP6 will be the RRI guidelines for grass-roots innovations. This evaluation framework and the experiences gained during the case actions will serve as a basis for these guidelines that will be formed in the spring 2023. We will produce an easy to approach guideline sets for the use of maker spaces, researchers and policy makers dealing with grass roots innovations on how to appreciate and address the particular responsibility questions that citizen-driven and citizen-oriented innovations settings face. The first suggestions of guidelines will be prepared by the Critical Making project team but it will be then elaborated in close collaboration with actors engaged in our case actions.

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